

PRIORITIES FOR PREPARING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL

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Annotation. This article describes the priorities for preparing preschool children for school. In particular, the concept and features of moral-volitional, mental and physical readiness were mentioned.

Keywords: preparation, group, school education, psychological characteristics, physical maturity, mental maturity, spiritual maturity, moral - volitional traits, vocabulary.

Introduction

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to the regulation on preschool education, a child receives preschool education at home, through independent education of parents or in preschool organizations with constant activity, as well as in preschool organizations for children who are not involved in preschool educational organizations, special groups or centers organized in schools, neighborhoods. Here they are engaged 2-3 times a week. Parents are allowed to choose a form of preschool education. In determining the readiness of a 6-7-year - old child for school education, pre-school children are considered the main condition- the readiness of the child for school should take into account the fact that it serves as a bridge for the way of life and activities of the preschool and school period, and the need to ensure free transfer to school education in The transition of a preschool child to school education always creates a significant change in his life, morality, interest and relationship. Therefore, it will be necessary to prepare a child or a child for school education, to introduce him to less difficult knowledge, understanding, skills and qualifications.

Physical fitness is explained by the fact that the child has developed wellness, movement skills and quality, hand muscles and visual-motor compatibility. Personal readiness, attitude to the environment, adults, peers, the world of plants, natural phenomena, implies the formation of a personal culture. Mental training involves the child's figurative and logical thinking, interest in knowledge, independence, self-control and knowledge of the main types of educational activities, such as observation, hearing, remembering, comparison. The effect of a child's schooling will depend more on his knowledge of his native language and how advanced he is in speech. Because the entire educational activity is built on these, that is, on the basis of such factors as the development of speech-Logic, independent thinking of the child without the help of adults, the development of language skills, storytelling, reasoning, the ability to interpret one's own imagination, to make it clear. It is also considered important for the development of practical intelligence for the child to receive education at school, that is, his ability to draw a sample, perform a narrative task to be told. Finally, special training implies teaching the child literacy and shaping his understanding of adequate mastery of the material of the school's 1st grade curriculum.

Discussion and results

The effectiveness of teaching children at school will largely depend on their level of training. School preparedness is determined through the requirements of the preschool organization and the family for a child of preschool age. The peculiarity of these requirements is associated with the new socio - psychological role of the student. The child must be prepared to carry out the tasks set before him. Admission to school is an important period in the life of a child associated with a change in the usual lifestyle, the system of relationships with those around him. For the first time in the life of a child, a central place is occupied by educational activities of social significance. In contrast to the free-play activities that are typical of the Urok, education will now be compulsory and 4 serious attitudes will be required from the first grader to rebuild the child's daily life process as a leading type of educational activity: the agenda will change, the time of free games will be kissed. The requirements for the independence and organization of the child, His workmanship and discipline are seriously increased. In relation to preschool childhood, the personal responsibility of the student to fulfill his behavior, obligations increases much more or less.

General preparation for school is such a level that the child has achieved in mental, spiritual, aesthetic and physical reproduction by the time of going to school that it provides the necessary basis for the child to actively penetrate into the new sharaotes of school education and the conscious possession of educational material. General training is expressed by a certain level of psychic development that the child reaches by the time of admission to school education. The concept of psychological training successfully sums up important quality indicators in the development of the child's psyche, going to Grade 1 from the point of view of school education. Psychological preparation for school education the child's desire to study in the student's passion for dividing cognitive activity and a sufficiently high level of contemplative operations include the child's acquisition of elements of educational activity, willpower and readiness based on manifestation at a certain level of Social Development. All the components of the psychological preparation of the child for school are reduced to bringing the child into the classroom team, the active possession of consciousness of educational material at school, the fulfillment of a wide range of school-related obligations. The special readiness of a child for school is an addition to the general psychological readiness to study at school. It is determined by the presence in the child of special knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary to study such educational subjects as mathematics and mother tongue.

The intensive work carried out in the preschool educational organization on the content of the simplest mathematical concepts in children, the cultivation of speech and the preparation for the acquisition of literacy provides the necessary level of special preparation of children for school education. It is desirable that a child who attends school is prepared for a new way of life for a new system of interaction with people, active mental activity. He must have reached a certain level of physical development in order to be able to make new serious commitments. There are several interconnected aspects in the content of the general readiness of the child for school (moral-volitional training to study), the important of which are spiritual, volitional, mental, physical training.

Moral-volitional readiness to study at school is expressed in the fact that by the end of preschool childhood, a child actively acquires a new social point of view in the development of moral behavior, will, moral feelings and consciousness, and reaches a level that allows him to build his relationship with his teacher and classmates on a moral basis. Moral volitional

readiness is manifested at a certain level of the development of personal behavior of a child of a large preschool age. In this relationship, the child's ability to control his own behavior, which develops throughout the age of preschool education: to consciously fulfill the rule or the demands of the educator, not to seek to restrain nervousness, to show perseverance in achieving the set goal, the skill of performing the deadlift against the fact that it attracts the necessary work, but distracts

The basis for the development of volatility in the behavior of the future student is the causes, mutual buy-sunders, which are formed by the end of the preschool age. In the content of moral-volitional readiness for school, as well as in the personal behavior of a child of a senior preschool age, such features as Independence Organization and discipleship are relevant. It is the ability to fulfill the rules of behavior that are inextricably linked with independence, to use the correct, usual methods of action in New conditions, to be willing to help. Independence and disorganization in behavior find its expression in orientation towards the goal in behavior with discipline, in being able to consciously organize its activities according to the rules adopted by preschool education in the organization, in being able to achieve and control the result of the activity, in coordinating its behavior with that of other children, in feeling personal responsibility for its actions. Another important component of moral - volitional readiness for school is the ability of a child to organize his interaction with adults and peers in accordance with the rules. Experience shows that adaptation to school study conditions directly depends on how successfully "public" qualities are formed in children in previous years: benevolent, respectful attitude towards friends, organizational skills, politeness, expression of care, presence in mutual assistance.

The presence of such a complex in the feelings of communalism in the behavior of a child can be an indicator of his moral readiness for school and create a high, positive spirit in dealing with his peers in the new community. Moral-volitional readiness for school is also expressed by a certain level of moral sensitivity and development of the child's consciousness. The most instructive in this regard is the understanding of the social significance of children's moral behavior, the development of the ability to independently assess their behavior in them, the formation of elements of responsibility, truthfulness, humanity and civic feelings. Moral-volitional readiness also includes a set of qualities that represent the attitude of a child of preschool age to work. This is a passion for work, respect for the work of those around them, the acquisition of the necessary labor qualifications.

An important component of mental readiness for school is the presence in a child entering school of a sufficiently wide wealth of knowledge about the environment, the world. This fund of knowledge is the necessary basis on which the teacher relies in the organization of his work. In the mental readiness of a child for school, the quality of the knowledge acquired by children is significant.

The indicator of the quality of knowledge is primarily the conscious acquisition of them by children; the clear and stratification of their imagination; the completeness of the content and volume of simple concepts; the ability to independently apply knowledge in solving educational and practical tasks understandable to themselves; regularity, that is, the ability of preschoolers to reflect understandable, important communication and relationships between things and phenomena.

The component of the child's mental preparation for school is that the child has developed cognitive activity to a certain extent. In this place, firstly, the growing volatility of

the process of cognition; the ability to voluntarily remember and repeat the material in terms of meaning, the planned perception of things and phenomena, the ability to purposefully solve the established cognitive and practical issues, and so on; secondly, the improvement of the quality of cognitive processes: accuracy of sensations, full and stratification of perception,; thirdly, it is important that the child has a cognitive relationship to the world around him, the acquisition of knowledge and the desire to study at school. In the formation of mental readiness for school, the general level of thinking activity of the future student is important.

In the regular, purposeful working conditions of the MTT regarding the mental education of children, the ability to comprehensively analyze things in children's (activity) thinking activities, the ability to use socially composed sensory trinkets in research on the characteristics and qualities of Science and phenomena, the ability to make simple generalizations based on basic communication in things and phenomena, the ability to Prospective students develop the elementary independence of mental activity: the ability to independently plan their own practical activity and carry it out according to a plan, the ability to set a simple cognitive task and solve it, and so on. Mental Readiness at school also includes the seizure of elements of educational activity by children. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

Conclusion

Children, in the conditions of regular education, by the end of preschool childhood, should acquire the main components of educational activity: the ability to accept an understandable educational task, understand the educator's instructions and accurately perform the work using the methods indicated by adults, the ability to achieve one result, control over the quality of their activities, behavior, tasks, the ability to How highly developed speech is is an important component of a child's mental preparation for school. The exact pronunciation of sound, the wealth of the dictionary, the ability to correctly state one's opinion logically and grammatically, the treatment of cultural speech – all this is a prerequisite for successful schooling. The composition of mental readiness also includes the initial basis of literacy, simple mathematical outlines, a sufficiently wide range of knowledge, skills and qualifications of the native language. Thus, mental readiness for school learning is composed of interconnected components of the mental and speech development of children. Cognitive activity, cognitive interests, methods of child thinking, understood systematized visions of the surrounding world and elements of imagination, speech and the unity of the general level of elementary educational activity create mental readiness in children to acquire educational material in school.

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